

NEXOGENESIS

STREAMLINING WATER RELATED POLICIES

D6.2 Communication activities report for M1-M18

Lead: Water Europe

Date: 02/02/2023

Project Deliverable

Project Number 101003881	Project Acronym NEXOGENESIS	Project Title Facilitating the next generation of effective and intelligent water-related policies, utilising artificial intelligence and reinforcement learning to assess the water-energy-food-ecosystem (WEFE) nexus
Instrument: H2020RIA		Thematic Priority LC-CLA-14-2020
Title D6.2 Communication activities report for M1-18		
Contractual Delivery Date 28/02/2023		Actual Delivery Date 28/02/2023
Start Date of the project 01 September 2021		Duration 48 months
Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable Water Europe		Document version 1
Dissemination level Public Confidential X		Deliverable Type Document, Report X
Authors (organisations) Water Europe		
Reviewers (organisations) Nina Olivier & Lisa Pourcher (G.A.C. Group)		

Abstract

The deliverable D6.2 presents all the communications activities completed within the first 18 months of the project, featuring in detail all the main materials, tools and channels used so far, to ensure the visibility of NEXOGENESIS project.

Keywords

Communications, activities, materials, branding, tools

Table of contents

Project Deliverable	2
Table of contents.....	4
1. Executive summary	6
2. Introduction	7
3. NEXOGENESIS Communications tools & activities.....	8
3.1 Branding	8
3.1.1 Logo	8
3.1.2 Style guide and templates	8
4. NEXOGENESIS online communication	10
4.1 Website.....	10
4.2 Social Media	11
4.3 Newsletters	14
4.4 Videos.....	17
4.5 Factsheets	19
4.6 Articles.....	21
4.7 Online events/webinars/workshops	23
5. NEXOGENESIS offline communication	24
5.1 Printed materials	24
5.1.1 General materials	24
5.1.2 Events materials	26
5.2 Organisation of events and project presentations during relevant events	27
6. Monitoring of the communication activities through KPIs	29
7. Conclusion and next steps	30

Table of figures

Figure 1: Screenshot of the NEXOGENESIS logo	8
Figure 3: Screenshot of NEXOGENESIS colour palette	9
Figure 2: Screenshot of the use NEXOGENESIS logo	9
Figure 4: Screenshot of the NEXOGENESIS ppt template	9
Figure 5: Screenshot of the NEXOGENESIS deliverable template	10
Figure 6: NEXOGENESIS Homepage	11
Figure 7: Project section.....	11
Figure 8: Case Studies	11

Figure 9: News and events.....	11
Figure 10: Different templates for the news and events articles on the website	12
Figure 11: YouTube.....	13
Figure 12: LinkedIn.....	14
Figure 13: Twitter	14
Figure 14: NEXOGENESIS 1st Newsletter edition.....	15
Figure 15: NEXOGENESIS 2nd Newsletter edition	16
Figure 16: Screenshots from the 1 st NEXOGENESIS video.....	17
Figure 18: Screenshots of the NXG case study 2 video.....	18
Figure 17: Screenshots of the NXG case study 1 video.....	18
Figure 20: Screenshots of the NXG case study 4 video.....	18
Figure 19: Screenshots of the NXG case study 3 video.....	18
Figure 21: Screenshots of the NXG case study 5 video.....	18
Figure 23: Screenshot from Dr Floor Brouwer interview	19
Figure 22: Screenshot from Janez Susnik’s interview.....	19
Figure 24: Screenshot from Lluís Echeverría Rovira interview	19
Figure 26: NEXOGENESIS factsheet #2	20
Figure 25: NEXOGENESIS factsheet #1	20
Figure 28: NEXOGENESIS factsheet #4	21
Figure 27: NEXOGENESIS factsheet #3	21
Figure 29: Screenshots from NEXOGENESIS online articles	22
Figure 30: Screenshots from NEXOGENESIS online meetings	23
Figure 31: Screenshot of NEXOGENESIS flyer	24
Figure 32: Screenshot of NEXOGENESIS poster.....	25
Figure 33: Screenshots of NEXOGENESIS poster templates.....	25
Figure 34: Screenshots of NEXOGENESIS roll-up (left) and the banner (above)	26
Figure 35: Screenshot from the press release template.....	26
Figure 36: NEXOGENESIS partners at the Ninth International Conference on Environmental Management, Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE 2022) and SECOTOX Conference.....	27
Figure 37: Screenshot from the 2 nd Stakeholder Workshop of Case Study 1	28
Figure 38: Banner of the 1 st stakeholder workshop of Case Study 2.....	28
Figure 39: Screenshot from Case Study 3 stakeholders’ workshop	28
Figure 40: Screenshot from Case Study 4 Workshop	28
Figure 41: Banner of the 1 st stakeholder workshop of Case Study 5.....	28

1. Executive summary

The deliverable 6.2 'Communications Activities Report for M1-18' has been developed in the context of NEXOGENESIS's Work Package (WP) 6 which aims to maximise the impact of the project by raising awareness, and communicating around project activities, while ensuring the dissemination, exploitation, sustainability, and added value creation during and beyond the project life cycle. This WP is linked to all other WPs as it supports all the project activities by providing adequate communication and dissemination materials and the right strategy for the results to be exploitable. Moreover, all the WPs are linked to this WP, as the WP6 activities are nurtured by all the project activities and results.

This report introduces the reader to the NEXOGENESIS branding identity and all the work the project's communications team has done from developing a distinguished visual character for the project to the creation of a series of online and print materials, as well as the promotion of the project through digital and physical means. The deliverable also makes reference to the monitoring aspect of the communications activities, providing updates on the key performance indicators reached up to month 18 of the project.

Overall, this report summarises all the communications activities that have taken place from September 2021 until the 18th month of the project. Two more reports on Communications activities are expected to be delivered, covering the period from M19-M36 of the project and the final period of NEXOGENESIS M36-M48.

2. Introduction

The deliverable 6.2 ‘Communications Activities Report for M1-18’ has been developed in the context of NEXOGENEIS Work Package 6 which is dedicated to maximizing the impact of the NEXOGENESIS project by raising awareness, communicating around the project activities, disseminating and exploiting the project results, while engaging a variety of stakeholder groups applying a multichannel communication approach.

The purpose of this document is to offer an overview of all the communication activities implemented within the first 18 months of the project, setting the basis for the promotion and widespread awareness of the NEXOGENESIS project and its achievements to a large audience throughout the whole duration of the project. All the existing materials and tools presented in this document will be maintained and updated, if necessary, over the course of the project, while further resources will be developed in response to project developments, results, as well as stakeholder needs and requirements.

Structured around six main chapters, this report introduces the readers to the visual identity and the branding of the NEXOGENESIS project, to continue with the online materials created and the channels used for the project, before moving on with the offline communication tools and the events where the project got disseminated. The communications KPIs reached up to the month 18th of the project are also presented.

In particular, now, the document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 3 presents the NEXOGENESIS branding, style guide and templates;
- Chapter 4 is dedicated to the online tools created, website, social media and newsletters and others;
- Chapter 5 is about the printed materials developed and the events in which NEXOGENESIS participated;
- Chapter 6 refers to the monitoring and KPIs reached;
- The document finishes with a summarising Conclusion Chapter.

3. NEXOGENESIS

Communications tools & activities

3.1 Branding

NEXOGENESIS is focused on facilitating the next generation of effective and intelligent water-related policies using artificial intelligence and machine learning to assess policy impacts on the WEFE nexus.

3.1.1 Logo

To capture and reflect the importance of the project's goals, a simple, easily recognizable, and self-explanatory brand identity was developed at the start of the project. The logo was developed in collaboration with the NEXOGENESIS core team (coordinator and WP leaders). As a first step, a short survey to the NEXOGENESIS core team was sent including questions about the colours of the logo, the tagline and the elements of the project to be highlighted through the logo. Based on the results of the survey and a discussion during the Steering Committee meeting, it has been decided that:

- The logo should be multicolour
- The tagline should be "Streamlining water related policies"
- The essential elements to be highlighted through the logo are the interlinkages between water, energy, food and ecosystems

Outcomes of these decisions were 4 logos which were submitted to a vote to decide upon the definitive logo of the project. The official NEXOGENESIS logo which best defines and symbolizes the nature and objectives of the project has been in unanimity decided upon the following:

Figure 1: Screenshot of the NEXOGENESIS logo

3.1.2 Style guide and templates

To ensure that the project has a coordinated visual identity and a consistent look and feel across all channels and based on the NEXOGENESIS logo, the communications team of the NEXOGENESIS project developed a detailed style guide that defines the way the logo can be used, the colour palette and the typography of the project, featuring specific guidelines for each case.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the use NEXOGENESIS logo

Figure 3: Screenshot of NEXOGENESIS colour palette

At the same time, Word and PowerPoint templates were also created so that all partners can use them when disseminating the project to external and internal audiences. A series of screenshots from the available materials are shown below.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the NEXOGENESIS ppt template

Figure 5: Screenshot of the NEXOGENESIS deliverable template

All these materials have been shared with all partners at M1 and included on the NEXOGENESIS SurfDrive (official project’s sharing platform).

4. NEXOGENESIS online communication

4.1 Website

The NEXOGENESIS website (<https://nexogenesis.eu/>) is the main source of information for the project and its developments. As the main communication resource to promote the project and its objectives, the website serves it with multiple roles:

- The one spot where all the information about the project can be found (project information, partners’ information, case studies, main outcomes, main results, etc.)
- A communications resource to update visitors about the project’s developments, events and news;
- A ‘download section’ with the project’s main communications, deliverables, publications, newsletter and factsheets;
- A direct link to social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube) and to the sign-up form for the newsletter.

The content of the website explains the NEXOGENESIS project to the general public in a simple, clear, and visually appealing way. The website is designed according to the project’s visual identity guidelines, making NEXOGENESIS instantly and easily recognisable. To ensure the successful promotion of the project and to sustain the interest of the target audience and attract new users, the website’s content is and will be maintained, continuously updated, and populated with new information throughout the lifetime of the project. Snapshots from the website are featured in the figures below.

Figure 6: NEXOGENESIS Homepage

Figure 7: Project section

Figure 8: Case Studies

Figure 9: News and events

The structure and content of the website has been elaborated in collaboration with the coordinator, IHE and case study leaders. Once validated, the structure and content was sent to an external designer who created the website using Wordpress. The website has been released at M5. The NEXOGENESIS website is composed of a landing page and 7 sections: 1. “Project” which includes 4 subsections “About NEXOGENESIS”, “Background”, “Objectives”, “The NEXOGENESIS solutions”, 2. “Consortium” which includes an overview of all the project partners, 3. “Case studies” which explains through 5 subsections the objectives, expected outcomes, partners and explanatory videos the 5 case studies, 4. “News & Events” including news articles, 5. “Downloads” which serves as a repository for all project communications, public deliverables, publications, newsletters and factsheets, 6. “Networking” including links and short descriptions of other projects and networks with which the project partners are creating synergies and collaboration, and 7. “Contact” which provides a space for website visitors to ask questions or to contact project partners and contact details of the project coordinator Dr. Janez Susnik.

Since the beginning of the project, the website has been updated as following:

- With the following 17 news and events articles:
 - “Kick-off meeting” released on the 2nd December 2021
 - “Join the NEXOGENESIS community” published on the 17th December 2021
 - “International symposium climate change & water 2022” released on the 17th December 2021
 - “Dresden Nexus Conference 2022 is coming up !” published on the 20th December 2021
 - “Our coordinator will speak at the Singapore International Water Week !” published on the 20th December 2021
 - “Case study #1: Nestos River Basin first workshop was a success !” released on the 8th March 2022
 - “Factsheet #1: What is the WEFE nexus ?” published on the 12th April 2022
 - “Case Study #3: Jiu River Basin, Lower Danube first stakeholders’ workshop will take place next May 19, 2022” online since the 20th April 2022
 - “Case study #4: Adige River Basin first stakeholder workshop” released on the 17th May 2022
 - “Factsheet #2: What is biophysical and socio-economic modelling” published on the 18th May 2022
 - “Case study #3: First stakeholders’ workshop was a success !” published on the 23rd May 2022
 - “Case study #5: First stakeholders’ workshop allowed us to do a mind map about the local needs” online since the 30th May 2022
 - “Case study #2: First nexus international stakeholder meeting in the Lielupe River basin” published on the 10th June 2022
 - “Factsheet #3: What is the system dynamics modelling approach ?” released on the 20th June 2022
 - “NEXOGENESIS WEFE nexus experts at the CEMEPE 2022 and SECO-TOX Conference in Mykonos published on the 24th June 2022
 - “NEXOGENESIS partners met for their annual project meeting in Riga, Latvia !” published on the 14th October 2022
 - “Case study #4: the 2nd stakeholders workshop took place !” released on the 18th October 2022

Different templates have been created for the different type of news as illustrated in the following figure. The goal is to diversify the visuals in the “News and events” section and to make it quickly recognisable what type of news it is.

Figure 10: Different templates for the news and events articles on the website

- Update of the partners’ logo and contact persons in the “Consortium” section

- Update of the “Downloads” section
 - The Newsletter #1 is available in a PDF format
 - The 4 factsheets are available in a PDF format
- Update of the “About NEXOGENESIS” section with the project presentation video
- Update of the Case studies’ sections with the case study presentation videos

4.2 Social Media

Social media presence is key for the project to accomplish its communication and dissemination objectives. The NEXOGENESIS project aims at building a strong online presence through its own channels but also through engaging with its partners’ channels, as well as the ones of targeted stakeholders that could function as multipliers of NEXOGENESIS’s messages and impact.

The NEXOGENESIS’s Communication Strategy (D6.1) makes reference to three main channels for the communication dissemination of the project’s news, events and results: Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube. These channels have been identified and selected as the best means to reach out to our target groups; to attract the relevant stakeholders for the project’s progress and to increase and maintain our stakeholders’ engagement and productivity throughout the whole duration of the project. The social media channels of the project have been active since the project’s launch and all the materials published through the accounts are in line with the project’s brand identity.

NEXOGENESIS’s YouTube account has gained 20 subscribers since its launch. Overall, the project has published 13 videos with an average of 79 views per videos. A snapshot of the NEXOGENESIS YouTube account is visible at Figure 9. More information about the videos are provided in section 4.4.

Figure 11: YouTube

The NEXOGENESIS's LinkedIn account currently engages with 271 followers and over the period September 2021 – January 2023 has published 56 posts with an average of 9.54 engagement rate and 11.714 total impressions.

The Twitter account of NEXOGENESIS has collected 370 followers. Since September 2021, NEXOGENESIS sent 104 tweets performing an average of 11.137 impressions and gaining a total of 176 likes. Snapshots of the NEXOGENESIS LinkedIn and Twitter accounts are shown in Figures 10 and 11.

Figure 12: LinkedIn

Figure 13: Twitter

Overall, NEXOGENESIS spreads its messages to a total of 644 online followers on a daily basis through its main social media channels.

4.3 Newsletters

Newsletters are one of the most powerful digital marketing tools at our disposal since they enable us to communicate directly with our readers in a personalized way by serving valuable content and relevant information straight to their inboxes. This is why email newsletters are a vital tool to increase a project's visibility and ensure its successful dissemination to its community. NEXOGENESIS's email newsletter allows the reader to get a clear overview of the project, its case studies, current developments, and the long-term benefits it brings.

To provide readers with a 360-degree update of what is happening in the project, the structure of the first newsletter included four indicative main sections:

- The first section was an introduction to the project and its case studies.
- The second section focused on the most important latest news and activities.
- The third section highlighted the occasions where the NEXOGENESIS project was presented.
- At the end of the newsletter, there was a part dedicated to extra news related to the projects followed by an agenda with a list of upcoming events.

While the intention is to follow a similar structure for NEXOGENESIS newsletters, the indicative structure above was used for the 1st edition, while the 2nd edition of the NEXOGENESIS newsletter was adjusted to the most current news and updates of the project. A specific news agenda will be decided for each edition of the newsletters, thus, every newsletter may consist of different sections or be presented in a different format to respond to our project’s news and our readers’ needs. Screenshots from the first and second newsletter prepared for the project follow below.

The first newsletter was sent to 50 recipients over MailChimp and it collected 58.0% of open rate, 29 opens and 11 clicks.

Figure 14: NEXOGENESIS 1st Newsletter edition

The second newsletter of the project was sent to 148 recipients over Mailchimp in February 2023 and it has collected so far 35.8% of open rate, 53 opens and 9 clicks.

Figure 15: NEXOGENESIS 2nd Newsletter edition

4.4 Videos

Videos have become the number one tool to clearly communicate a story. This is why, over the last 18 months, NEXOGENESIS has moved forward publishing a variety of videos to promote the project's case studies but also to inform the general public about the NEXOGENESIS's main topics. The communications team of the NEXOGENESIS project has released 13 videos through YouTube with the intention to enhance the online visibility of the project and strengthen the project's dissemination efforts.

The 1st NEXOGENESIS project video introduces the project's objectives, case studies and expected results. The video is structured under four pillars: 1) introduction of the WEFE nexus, 2) the targeted challenges of NEXOGENESIS, 3) the overall impact expected by the project and 4) the five case studies and the ambitions NEXOGENESIS.

The project's video is available on the NEXOGENESIS [YouTube Channel](#) but also on the website.

Figure 16: Screenshots from the 1st NEXOGENESIS video

The project presentation video has also been developed with translated subtitles and share with all partners on SurfDrive. It is available with French, German, Italian, Spanish and Greek subtitles.

NEXOGENESIS has also published five case studies' videos aimed at describing the WEFE related challenges addressed on a local level and how the project intends to approach to tackle these issues. The five videos scored an average of 59 views. The playlist with the 5 videos is available [here](#). Screenshots of the 5 case studies video are illustrated in the figures below. These videos have also been shared with case study partners with subtitles in the local languages to be used locally for events or local dissemination.

Figure 17: Screenshots of the NXG case study 1 video

Figure 18: Screenshots of the NXG case study 2 video

Figure 19: Screenshots of the NXG case study 3 video

Figure 20: Screenshots of the NXG case study 4 video

Figure 21: Screenshots of the NXG case study 5 video

Besides the case studies' videos, NEXOGENESIS featured on its YouTube channel three interviews. In the first one, Dr Floor Brouwer, researcher at Wageningen in the Netherlands, reveals the history of the WEFE nexus and how the concept has evolved over the years until it was crucial to have the interdependencies between water, energy, food and nexus recognised. This interview was taken at the occasion of the CEMEPE 2022 and a joint meeting with the COST Action NEXUSnet in June 2022 in Mykonos. The first interview received 108 views. The interview is available [here](#).

The second interview has Janez Susnik as protagonist, who is a senior researcher at the IHE Delft and coordinator of the NEXOGENESIS project. In less than two minutes, he offers a glimpse of the project's goals and objectives. The video also contains a description of the project by all partners: each partner gives a word that best describes the project. The video is available on [YouTube](#) and website. Overall, the video has reached 119 views.

The third and last interview, up to now, is with Lluís Echeverría Rovira, researcher from EURECAT who explains the NEXOGENESIS tool. The video is available [here](#).

Figure 22: Screenshot from Janez Susnik's interview

Figure 23: Screenshot from Dr Floor Brouwer interview

Figure 24: Screenshot from Lluís Echeverria Rovira interview

It is planned to release the following videos, one every 2-3 weeks:

- The NEXOGENESIS Case study #1 by Maria P Papadopoulou from NTUA
- The co-creation of the WEFE nexus governance and water policy streamlining by Stefania Munaretto from KWR leader of the WP1
- The NEXOGENESIS Case study #2 by Ingrida Brēmere from BEF
- The NEXOGENESIS WEFE Nexus Footprint by Dr. Gareth Simpson from JAWS, developer of the footprint
- The NEXOGENESIS Case study #3 by Valentina Nano from BDG
- The Policy at the heart of NEXOGENESIS by Tamara Avellan from AVA, leader of the Task 6.5 on policy impact
- The NEXOGENESIS Case study #4 by Silvia Cocuccioni from EURAC
- The NEXOGENESIS Case study #5 by Dr. Gareth Simpson from JAWS

All these interviews have been taken during the consortium meeting in September 2022 in Riga, Latvia. The focus was to present the different components of the project and to explain what the expected results by the end of the project are. It is planned to take another series of interviews during the next consortium meeting in September 2023 in Tours, France focusing more on the advancements and results achieved so far in the case studies, WPs and developments of tools.

4.5 Factsheets

Factsheets are an essential tool to display key information in a visual manner that can be easily understood by the reader. NEXOGENESIS published four factsheets available on the website

and the YouTube channel. The factsheets were duplicated to a video format and in a slideshow format in order to share a more interactive version on social media channels.

The [first factsheet](#) 'What is the WEFE nexus?' introduces the reader to the concept of the WEFE nexus and how it is integrated in the NEXOGENESIS project. The [second factsheet](#) titled 'Biophysical and socio-economic modelling?' provides some definitions to better understand the concept of "biophysical and socioeconomic modelling and how it is linked with NEXOGENESIS.

The [third factsheet](#) titled 'System dynamics modelling approach' offers a short overview of what the system dynamics modelling approach is and how it is relevant to the NEXOGENESIS project. The [fourth factsheet](#) 'The importance of stakeholders engagement' introduces the reader to the definition of stakeholder engagement, stressing how crucial it is for the co-creation and validation of the modelling and policy-related outputs in the NEXOGENESIS project.

Figure 25: NEXOGENESIS factsheet #1

Figure 26: NEXOGENESIS factsheet #2

Figure 27: NEXOGENESIS factsheet #3

Figure 28: NEXOGENESIS factsheet #4

Several more factsheets are planned by the end of the year as following:

- Factsheet #5 on Transboundary water diplomacy
- Factsheet #6 on River contracts
- A series of factsheets on the developments in the different case studies

4.6 Articles

On the project's website 17 articles have been published including news about the different events in which NEXOGENESIS was presentation, main activities of the project, etc. See Section 4.1.

Moreover, the NEXOGENESIS project has attracted attention not only through its own channels, but also made appearance on partners' and other external websites. At least 25 blog posts and news articles have been dedicated to NEXOGENESIS over this period. The screenshots below demonstrate NEXOGENESIS online visibility in different websites.

Figure 29: Screenshots from NEXOGENESIS online articles

4.7 Online events/webinars/workshops

As some part of the activities of the NEXOGENESIS project has coincided with the outbreak of the COVID19 pandemic, a number of events has taken place through digital means. The kick-off meeting of the project was held online in September 2021, allowing partners to connect from their respective locations. Other meetings of NEXOGENESIS Case studies and its stakeholder workshops were available in hybrid format, enabling the physical and online presence of participants. In parallel with these, NEXOGENESIS also made its presence felt to other online conferences as presented in the table 1 below. The screenshots below offer a glimpse of some of these meetings. Detailed information on these meetings is featured on the project's news and events [page](#).

Event Name	Date	Partners Involved	Type of contribution
Watershare Webinar Series	17/02/2022	IHE	Presentation
Singapore International Water Week - Water Convention	17-21/04/2022	IHE	Presentation
Dresden Nexus Conference 2022	23/05/2022	IHE, KWR	Presentation & poster

Table 1: NEXOGENESIS participation to online external events

Figure 30: Screenshots from NEXOGENESIS online meetings

5. NEXOGENESIS offline communication

5.1 Printed materials

As defined in the NEXOGENESIS Communications Strategy (D6.1), the print dissemination actions for the promotion of the project are of high importance throughout the whole duration of the project.

5.1.1 General materials

Responding to the different needs of the project at each stage, the development of a series of attractive promotional materials is key for the promotion of the project's developments in a professional and engaging way. Either in a traditional print format or an electronic one, the promotional materials can be widely disseminated and shared on a range of occasions from formal conferences and NEXOGENESIS workshops to social media posts and email campaigns. The promotional materials developed, so far, aim to present the objectives and solutions of the project, the concept of the project, key information about the project and present the case studies in an easily understandable and captivating way for the general public. So far, the project has produced one flyer and one poster, as featured in Figures 26 and 27.

Figure 31: Screenshot of NEXOGENESIS flyer

Facilitating the next generation of effective and intelligent water-related policies utilising artificial intelligence and reinforcement learning to assess the water-energy-food-ecosystem (WEFE) nexus

THE CHALLENGES

Skills in the WEFE nexus are driven by changes in biophysical (climate, precipitation, land cover) and human (economic development, agriculture, urban growth) conditions. Continuing current consumption rates imply depleting resource and ecological assets – where resources are extracted at a faster rate than they are replaced. To effectively manage resources and avoid conflicts between users, many relevant policies must be intelligently designed to address resource interconnections at multiple spatial scales.

THE PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- Identify and model WEFE nexus interlinkages
- Reduce uncertainties of how new policies and stakeholder behavior affect the nexus through the Integration Self-Learning Nexus Assessment Engine (ISLNAE)
- Develop and apply a new WEFE Nexus Footprint
- Demonstrate and validate the NEXOGENESIS framework including the application of the ISLNAE in five case studies
- Support out-scaling of the NEXOGENESIS framework to other basins and other applications

THE CASE STUDIES AND EXPECTED RESULTS

Linkage River Basin
Linkage and Ukraine

Understand the potential of the WEFE nexus to provide the water for economic activities in this transboundary river basin. Investigate how the uncertainty and spatial heterogeneity of the WEFE nexus can be managed. Assess policy implications on development, consumption, and energy for water, agriculture, and industry.

Lower Danube Basin
Romania, Bulgaria, and Hungary

Assess the potential of the WEFE nexus to provide the water for economic activities in this transboundary river basin. Investigate how the uncertainty and spatial heterogeneity of the WEFE nexus can be managed. Assess policy implications on development, consumption, and energy for water, agriculture, and industry.

Adige River Basin
Italy

Assess the potential of the WEFE nexus to provide the water for economic activities in this transboundary river basin. Investigate how the uncertainty and spatial heterogeneity of the WEFE nexus can be managed. Assess policy implications on development, consumption, and energy for water, agriculture, and industry.

Nestos River Basin
Greece and Turkey

Assess the potential of the WEFE nexus to provide the water for economic activities in this transboundary river basin. Investigate how the uncertainty and spatial heterogeneity of the WEFE nexus can be managed. Assess policy implications on development, consumption, and energy for water, agriculture, and industry.

Inkomoti-Uusuthu
South Africa

Assess the potential of the WEFE nexus to provide the water for economic activities in this transboundary river basin. Investigate how the uncertainty and spatial heterogeneity of the WEFE nexus can be managed. Assess policy implications on development, consumption, and energy for water, agriculture, and industry.

THE NEXOGENESIS SOLUTIONS

- The NEXOGENESIS self-learning nexus assessment engine (ISLNAE)
- A WEFE Nexus Footprint: a composite indicator
- User-validated policy packages

START DATE: 01 September 2021 DURATION: 48 months BUDGET: 5M€

Figure 32: Screenshot of NEXOGENESIS poster

At the same time, the NEXOGENESIS communications team has created a poster template of four different structures to enable partners to portray information about the project in various ways. The editable template facilitates the consortium to communicate about the project using tailored materials for each communication and dissemination occasion.

The figure shows four distinct poster templates for NEXOGENESIS. Each template features the project logo at the top and a central map of Europe. The templates vary in their layout of text boxes, image placeholders, and graphic elements, providing different visual structures for communicating project information.

Figure 33: Screenshots of NEXOGENESIS poster templates

5.1.2 Events materials

More event-related materials have been also produced that can be tailored and used by all partners in the occasion of events organised within the framework of NEXOGENESIS project. In addition to the flyer and the poster presented above, a roll-up banner has been created as featured in figure 34, and a press release template to facilitate partners to announce the event in a consistent way in figure 35.

Figure 34: Screenshots of NEXOGENESIS roll-up (left) and the banner (above)

Figure 35: Screenshot from the press release template

5.2 Organisation of events and project presentations during relevant events

Up to the 18th month of the project, NEXOGENESIS partners joined five face to face events, either to present the project and disseminate the project's promotional materials or to network with others, as indicated in the table 2 below.

Event Name	Date	Partners Involved	Location	Type of contribution
Climate Change and Water 2022	02/06/2022	IHE,UNT	Tours, France	Presentation
Ninth International Conference on Environmental Management, Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE 2022) and SECOTOX Conference	03-09/06/2022	UTH, KWR, GAC	Mykonos, Greece	Presentation
Workshop on water storage policy- Building hydraulic knowledge and the food-water-energy nexus	4/07/ 2022	Eurac	Padoa, Italy	Presentation
International Mountain Conference	11-15/09/2022	Eurac	Innsbruck, Austria	Presentation
Earth System Governance conference 2022	22/10/2022	KWR	Toronto	Presentation

Table 2: NEXOGENESIS participation to face-to-face events

Figure 36: NEXOGENESIS partners at the Ninth International Conference on Environmental Management, Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE 2022) and SECOTOX Conference

The Case study leaders also organised a series of stakeholders' workshops across the 18 months of the project. The screenshots below offer a glimpse of some of these occasions.

Figure 37: Screenshot from the 2nd Stakeholder Workshop of Case Study 1

Figure 38: Banner of the 1st stakeholder workshop of Case Study 2

Figure 39: Screenshot from Case Study 3 stakeholders' workshop

Figure 40: Screenshot from Case Study 4 Workshop

Figure 41: Banner of the 1st stakeholder workshop of Case Study 5

6. Monitoring of the communication activities through KPIs

All the communication activities throughout the project are closely monitored and assessed based on a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) indicatively specified for each channel and phase of the project. Excel monitoring forms are set up and distributed among partners to capture all the communications efforts that happened within the consortium. The forms are sent out to partners on a periodic basis.

The table 1 below presents the main communication and dissemination tools and the KPIs set. An additional column has been added, presenting the updated figures up to the month 18 of the project, demonstrating that both the online and the physical communications activities of the project are on great track.

Table 3: Communication activities KPIs

KPIs	1 st Period (M1-18)	2 nd Period (M19-36)	3 rd period (M36-48)	Overall	KPIs reached for the 1 st reporting period (M1-18)
Number of website visitors	1100	1100	1300	3000+	2802
Number of followers on Twitter and LinkedIn	100	100	150	300+	643
Number of project publications/press releases	4	7	11	20+	8
Number of scientific publications	10	16	28	50+	4
Number of policy briefs		1	2	3	0
Number of organised events	0	4	6	10+	0
Number of participants in the organised events		30	30	50+	0
Number of newsletters	2	3	3	8	2
Number of newsletter subscribers	50	100	100	200+	149
Number of news on the website	10	10	10	at least 6 per year	17
Number of events in which the project participated in	6	16	15	30+	8
Number of flyers created	0	1	0	1	1
Number of posters created	0	1	0	1	1

7. Conclusion and next steps

The aim of Deliverable D6.2 has been to present all the Communication activities accomplished up to the 18th month of the project. Starting with a strong brand identity for the NEXOGENESIS project and by creating and making use of a series of attractive communications materials and tools, the promotion and dissemination of the project's objectives and developments have taken place over the first period of the project in an easily understandable, engaging, and appealing way.

This report aspired to provide detailed information on all the work done for creating the NEXOGENESIS brand identity; the online materials developed and tools used, as well as the print materials produced throughout the first eighteen months of the project, together with the events where the project was presented. All these materials are to be used by the project partners, and thus, they are available on NEXOGENESIS SurfDrive so that partners can download them and communicate properly about the project, using materials that are in line with the project's official brand identity.

According to the figures presented in the monitoring table, it is evident that the communications activities are on good track and the diligent update of the online tools of the project will be an ongoing activity until the end of the project, together with the printed and digital promotional materials that will be updated with the project's outcomes, ensuring that the consortium always has available materials to communicate successfully about the project.

Until the end of the project, two more reports on Communications activities are expected to be delivered, covering the period from M19-M36 of the project and the final period of NEXOGENESIS M36-M48.

